

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Biostimulants increased soil nematode taxa that feed on bacteria and fungi in Mediterranean vegetable fields, with no effect on earthworms communities

During three years, we rotated in SE Spain (semiarid Mediterranean climate) the following crops: 1. Potato, from 22/12/2020 to 04/06/2021; 2. Broccoli, from 5/10/2021 to 10/01/2022; 3. Melon, from 29/03/2022 to 14/07/2022; and 4. Potato, from 16/12/2022 to 15/05/2023. The crops were established under drip irrigation and mineral fertilization. Four different fertilization treatments were designed, where we reduced mineral fertilizer to partially replace it by biostimulants: i) Inorganic fertilizers applied at the nutritional demands of the crop (F100); ii) The 50% of the rate of inorganic fertilizers added in F100 (F50); iii) F50 + the application of a formulation of nitrogen-fixing and phosphorus and potassium solubilizing bacteria (BA); and iv).

F50 + the application of a formulation of bacteria and non-mycorrhizal fungi (BA+FU). The number and biodiversity of nematodes was not affected by the addition of biostimulants, but their composition changed compared to full inorganic fertilisation. In addition, biostimulants addition led to decreased functional complexity of the nematode community, increasing nematode taxa that feed on bacteria and fungi. There was no effect of fertilisation on earthworms abundance and diversity. The use of biostimulants can be fostered in Mediterranean horticulture to reduce the dependency on mineral fertilizers.

1. Broccoli crop under drip irrigation in SE Spain

KEYWORDS

Vegetables, rotations, biostimulants, soil, nematodes, earthworms

AUTHORSHIP

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

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